

Fostering Innovation, Integration and Inclusion Through
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Job Satisfaction Factors of Employee
in Virtual Workplace: Review

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ABSTRACT

Business success depends on Job satisfaction of employees. It is essential key part of organization. There is need to understand factors behind job satisfaction and need of employee for better output. It will help in increasing business activities. Now a day's, most employees work at virtual place. Knowing his or her factors of job satisfaction of such employees, it will get most important source of information for improving companies' overall growth, increasing product and services level. There are various factors affects on Job satisfaction; it may be common or different. This paper is focusing on literature reviews of paper on Job Satisfaction factors of employees who work in virtual workplace. To Knows Job Satisfaction Factors of Employee will helps to all.

KEYWORDS: Job satisfaction factors, Telecommuting, Telecommuter

INTRODUCTION

In today's computational, technological environment employ's or worker are work in virtual place. The mobile workforce or telecommuting or remote worker is a relatively widely famous concept in India. Yes!! Telecommuting makes the workforce more efficient, cuts costs. They are helping for protecting the environment. Many organizations are developing telecommuting programmers as a way to draw new employees to work and use such Virtual environment. In today's day there is tight labor market, companies that offer flexibility. Employers, employee & end user require workplace flexibility. With this advancement of communications and information technology concepts has ability to log on the company's network from any location by using hardware devices like notebook computers, smart mobile phones and handheld devices has given rise to a trend of mobile computing and telecommuting.

Employees work at virtual network they are telecommuting or teleworker or teleworking. Work related travel can be replaced by use of information technology, telecommunications. The employees work at home or at a related telework center using communication tools, such as phone, fax, modem, Internet teleconferencing, e-mail or I M. Employees can perform his or her work duties from a remote location. Mostly such work presently found in Europe, U.S, Canada and other country. Telecommuting refers to a full or part time flexible work arrangement; which is essentially combines the use of telecommunication technologies with the concept of the flexible workplace. Here are some important terms to understand that is as, an electronic cottage is a reference for telecommuting it referred to a home equipped with a computer, modem, telephone line or other that allowed an individual to perform

work in the home while connected to a remote computer site. A flexible work arrangement means adjustment working times and locations for a better work-life balance. Job satisfaction means positive or negative feelings employees have about their job. The Level of telecommuting is the number of days spent telecommuting. A non-telecommuter is an employee who performs job duties at the organizational facility. Telecommuters are that employees who allowed perform organizational duties from home or other locations using technology. Telecommuting or telework is an arrangement between an organization and an employee to work from a location other than the organization's business site. Teleworking is an alternate work arrangement. This has transformed the workplace which allows workers to fulfill their job assignment from any location away from the traditional office. Such work

arrangement has been growing in popularity due to various factors. Employee's job satisfaction is important to organization and every one. Employees job satisfaction affect on business growth. Understanding factors behind job satisfaction of employees is important in today's day. Technology increased rapidly, most of works are complete in remote place. A modern employee doesn't want travel for simple work. In today's modern environments Virtual offices have been a growing up and It have been used to improve organizational performance for several decades. This paper understands Job Satisfaction factors of employees who work in virtual workplace by review of literature. It helps all.

Reviews of Literature

Smith, Patmos, Pitts, (2018) in paper 'Channel Satisfaction, Personality, and Job Satisfaction for Teleworking Employees' He stated that personality factors, offer great insight into workplace behaviors. It was understood that some teleworkers experience greater levels of job satisfaction than others. He was used Big Five personality traits: openness, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness, and neuroticism and the communication channel satisfaction of e-mail, instant messaging, phone, and video communication for finding the job satisfaction of teleworkers. Author concluded that there were a significant relationship was not present between neuroticism and job satisfaction; and significant relation found in communication channel satisfaction: (e-mail, video technologies, instant messaging, and phone communications and job satisfaction). They had experienced greater levels of job satisfaction.

Brian Hill (2018) in the article 'Factor Affecting Job Satisfaction' he was told that with the reference of Society for Human Resource Management: 7 Strategies for Keeping Employees Happy at Work; and Forbes: Promoting Employee Happiness Benefits Everyone. According to author Employee's overall satisfaction was by some of factors like working condition, opportunity, work load, respect from other, relationship and financial rewards.

Regina (2016), in dissertations 'Factors that Affect Job Satisfaction and Work Outcomes of Virtual Workers', Author was exploring the lived experiences of virtual workers. His purpose was explore the lived experiences of virtual workers so that he was a qualitative phenomenological approach for research, He was addressed a real world problem within the virtual workplace. They concluded that the most valuable asset of organization and society: individual worker. Work, place of work, Life Balance, Training, Technical Support, Communication and Flexibility are affect on satisfaction of Job.

Ratna and Kaur, (2016) in article 'The impact of Information Technology on Job Related Factors like Health and Safety, Job Satisfaction, Performance, Productivity and Work Life Balance', Journal of Business & Financial Affairs' researcher told that in 21st century there was increased Information Technology use so that digital computing, combined with the use of telecommunications technology. Work was done at virtual network.

LaShawn Johnson (2016), in the research of 'Predictors of Job Satisfaction Among Telecommuters' He told that there was millions of people work in alternative locations outside of corporate offices In the United States. They told that such type of work has many different names: telecommuting,

mobile office, teleworking, working from/at home or other, alternate work location, and flexible work arrangements. It indicates that an employee works from a location other than the employer's business office. According to him there is relationship between level of telecommuting, gender, age, and employee job satisfaction that means age, gender, and level of telecommuting can predict job satisfaction

Jindan Zhang (2016), in the article 'The Dark Side of Virtual Office and Job Satisfaction' He told that virtual offices developed for organizational performance. Many companies or organization was facing various experience the challenges, problems and policy. Author was studied the changes in employees work life towards job satisfaction. He was explained in two parts; first was describing the changes in virtual office from four perspectives such as Communication, social relations, achievement recognition and work-life balance; and second was capturing the impact of work life which represented by job satisfaction. Author concluded that change of communication with co-workers, social relations of achievement recognition and work-life balance virtual offices; it can be significantly predict job satisfaction of employees.

Kelley (2015) in the thesis 'Flexible Work Schedules, Virtual Work Programs, and Employee Productivity, According to him there was increasing change, computation, business leaders need to increased alternative work programs that means of change work type to virtual environment. According to this changes need he was focused and studied spillover theory, motivator-hygiene theory etc. He was studied the strategies that business leaders or say owner or stockholder use for flexible work schedules and virtual work programs He was concluded that Work-life balance and work-life satisfaction may have an effect on productivity in the workplace. Business leaders was used various techniques for developing, implementing, and maintaining flexible work schedules and virtual work programs. Some of them strategies was considered for employee productivity, working hours, communication, virtual office setups, job satisfaction, and quality of life. Organization were considered for achievements of employees by using set or increased the standard set of virtual working hours, Flexible/Alternative Work Schedule Policy, virtual communication, Special Telecommuting Policy and quality of life is important for virtual employees.

Allied Telecom (2015) in article '8 Reasons Why Virtual Workforces Work' they given eight reason benefit in business when the virtual workforces work involved these was as, Employees feel happy in virtual work, they were less absent in job, employees was work harder, attracted better candidates, work Flexibility helps keep better employees, benefited for traditional workforces, manage easy. According to them virtual workforces help businesses in the modern world. Many employees happy and appreciate of such flexibility of working from home and better choice to candidate/ employees.

Sneha, Shailaja (2014) in research article 'Comparative Study of Job Satisfaction between Employees of Virtual Teams and Traditional Teams' author was investigated differences between virtual and traditional team employees on the level of job satisfaction. She was explained about virtual team who are a group of people who interact through interdependent tasks guided by common purpose that works

across space, time, and organizational boundaries with links strengthened by webs of communication technologies with reference of Lipnack and Stamps, 1997 and Job Satisfaction is pleasurable emotional state towards their job; it is a result of employee perception of how well their job provides those things that are viewed as important by the employees with reference of Locke. 1976. Author concluded that Overall job satisfaction was higher in virtual team employees than traditional team employees. Job satisfaction role is important in organization for performance, productivity and increasing turnover.

Russell, Steven (2013) in the article 'The Dark Side of Working in a Virtual World: An Investigation of the Relationship between Workplace Isolation and Engagement among Teleworkers' author told that there was a dark side for those working in virtual world. There were various issues of workplace isolation. There can be requiring employee engagement in the organization. It can be seen as major and critical problems that employers will have to deal with. Author was investigated the relationship between workplace isolation and engagement among teleworkers. Researcher finally told that 90 million employees were engaged in this field of work in the future. it was important for managers to understand the downsides of utilizing this form of worker environment. Managers were needed to consider methods of daily contact with these employees. There must be relationship between workplace isolation and engagement among teleworkers is important. They found that critical issues between work-place isolation and employee engagement among those who were work in a virtual environment.

Farah, Abdul, Mohd Zin (2012) in the article 'Analysis Of Literature Review On Factors Influencing The Adoption Of Telecommuting' told that there was increasing private vehicle use in the International Islamic University Malaysia (IIUM) . There were traffic issues so employees to be considered for telecommuting which was an alternative work option. Most staff was adopted for telecommuting staffs. It was useful for reducing the peak hour traffic in IIUM. Researcher was investigating the perception of IIUM employees on various aspects of telecommuting and shown some factors influencing employees' preferences towards telecommuting. Researcher was reviewed some of the Factors which was Influencing for the Choice of Adopting in Telecommuting Mode. According to them factors like Personal and Household, Work-related, Travel-related are significant impact on telecommuting adoption.

Tshepisho Tabane (2011) in research paper 'Job satisfaction in virtual and face-to-face teams for multiple generations in the workplace' Author she was investigated associations between levels of job satisfaction in virtual and face-to-face to teams for multiple generations. According to his study, there was no relationship found how multiple generations feel about job satisfaction. There was enough evidence to suggest that there was a significant difference in Job satisfaction levels for multiple generations in different work teams. The level of utilization of technology does not influence job satisfaction level differently for multiple generations.

Valerie, Debra, Kurt, Jennifer, Michelle (2010) in paper 'Comparing Telework Locations and Traditional Work Arrangements: Differences In Work-Life Balance Support,

Job Satisfaction, And Inclusion' studied, examined and report on Employees work-life balance (WLB) job satisfaction and its function by considering work location. He was used Multiple regression analyses for identifying differences in WLB support, job satisfaction by work locations. According to his research he found that main office and home based workers had similar high levels of Work Life Balance support and job satisfaction. He also told that main office workers had higher levels of Work Life Balance support than satellite and client-based workers. Job satisfaction affects on Work Place. Worker at home they are depend on technology and in office they use technology as well as manually work in the time technical disturbance. Author Concluded that there was good if you were allow employees flexibility in work locations choice, was came positive outcomes.

Kathryn, Michael (Nov 2010), in article 'Why Teleworkers are More Satisfied with Their Jobs than are Office-Based Workers: When Less Contact is Beneficial, Journal of Applied Communication Research' According to his study, author was examined the extent to which telework affection of job satisfaction through the employees experiences of work - life conflict, stress which was occur by meetings and interruptions, perceived organizational politics, and information exchange. He told that work- life conflicts had desirable benefits. Employees' job satisfaction decreases when their work and personal responsibilities was interfered with each other. Telework was affordable more boundary control and power to diminish interruptions and distractions. It can be relieving stress and be positively related to job satisfaction. They stated that teleworkers were satisfied due to their reduced exposure to organizational politics. Job satisfaction could be negatively affected by quality information exchange. Further, He was concluded that telework and job satisfaction link connected with work-life conflict, info exchange, Quality of Info, Stress from interruptions, general policy and politics. Author were used a multiple mediation approach and path analysis and shown that telework was affects job satisfaction through the experiences of work-life conflict, stress due to meetings and interruptions, perceived organizational politics, information exchange.

Nicholas (June 2010) in article 'Job satisfaction, morale, and cultural diversity: Factors influencing worker perspectives, expectations, and management strategies', He was concerned the impact of the physical environment morale, the stress and morale, the relationship with management on job satisfaction. According author the relationship of the workers to management, lower to upper level management had effect upon the job satisfaction. He was told that social climate of the environment of the organization had impacted the retention rates, its morale and job satisfaction of the employees.

Brie Weiler Reynolds, Senior Career Specialist (2011) in blog post title "Telecommuting or Teleworking - What's the Difference?" told that tele' means "distance"; Teleworking can be referred to working from a distance. Telecommuting can be referred specifically to the removal of a daily travel; she was also told that Telecommuters was always teleworkers, but teleworkers are not necessarily telecommuters.

Venktesh (53312) was shared article with title 'Factors Influencing Job Satisfaction' on website

yourarticlelibrary.com told that organization factors- salary, promotion, company policy; work environmental factors – supervision, work group, work condition; work itself- job security, variety, interest of work; and personal factors Age, Tenure, personality are sources of job satisfaction.

Dawn H. Coveyduck (April 1997), thesis was 'Investigation of Selected Factors on Job Satisfaction among Telecommuters' Author told that converging social, economic and technological forces was prompted massive decentralization of the workplace or location of work. Company had made a regular with formal arrangement for employees to work at home or remote location. Telecommuters enjoyed and shown high job satisfaction, work autonomy, commitment to the organization. According to him, Demographic variables had predicted feeling toward the organization. There was complex relationship between personality factors such as attitudes, needs and expectations, and demographic variables as moderators of job satisfaction levels. He told that there was high level job satisfaction by organizational support. There was importance of autonomy and inter-role conflict in job satisfaction. Employers must be help their employees or telecommuters. Work team is important for satisfaction of employee. They must be maintaining good relationship with manager.

According to **Mr. M. D. Mohite** (2017) with reference blogs, presentation, social comments told that job satisfaction factors depends or affects on micro and macro environments. Employee satisfaction feeling is in his or her happiness. There are various factors which may be temporary based or permanent based. If we daily implement various policy in favor of employee and employer will turns both side profit. According to **Dr. R. V. Kulkarni** (2016) in IT management lecture told that Virtual Workplace development is modern technology. Employees whose doesn't want travel, want work from home or remote location then it is right place for work of such employee. Virtual Workplace will change life working experience.

Conclusion:

In modern days there is need of modern working techniques. Employers, employee & end user are showing interest such workplace flexibility. Technology helps to achieve present need so work flexibility. Employees are work in virtual workplace. Understanding job satisfaction factor is important. Job satisfaction factors of employees; whose are work in virtual workplace mentioned on the basis on literature review. Researcher cannot explain which most important factors affect on job satisfaction. This paper is on initial stage of the study, there are not direct findings. It is highly expected that this paper would provide important factors of Job satisfaction to respective reader. According to above literature of reviews and study of job satisfaction factors of employees whose are work in virtual workplace. Here are some important Factors that influenced on job satisfaction. which are Place, Work, Time, Stress, Gender, Age, Experience, Immediate superior, Relationship, Communication, Technology, Payment, Policy, Security, Responsibility, Personal, dependency, Guidance, Achievement, Traveling, Social, Status, Trust, Feedback, Help, Psychology and Law. There may be positive relationship between demographic characteristics/ variable with job satisfaction of employees in virtual workplace. Job satisfaction depends on Employees and Employers percentage of involvements between them. Here saying that

Satisfaction is inner feeling which may be variable that depends on situation, facts and tense.

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